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Trade-offs between nutrient circularity and environmental impacts in the management of organic waste

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23 **ABSTRACT**

24

25 Measuring the circularity of resources is essential to assess the performance of a circular
26 economy. This work aims at proposing a metrics to quantify the circularity of the components
27 recovered from waste. The developed indicator was applied to study the circularity of nutrients
28 within a system that handles the organic waste (OW) generated in the Spanish region of
29 Cantabria and uses the recovered products as soil amendment to grow corn. In order to
30 determine the optimal configuration of the system, a superstructure comprising alternative unit
31 processes for the management of OW and the recovered products was developed. A multi-
32 objective MILP problem was formulated under two policy scenarios with different source
33 separation rates. Six objective functions were identified: the circularity indicators of carbon,
34 nitrogen and phosphorus, and their associated environmental impacts (global warming, marine
35 eutrophication and freshwater eutrophication). The model was fed with the Life Cycle
36 Assessment results obtained with EASETECH and the nutrient flows in the agriculture subsystem,
37 which were calculated with DNDC. It was concluded that improving nutrient circularity
38 paradoxically leads to eutrophication impacts, and increasing the source separation rate of OW
39 has a positive effect on the carbon footprint of the system.

40

41

42 **Table Of Contents**

43

44 INTRODUCTION

45

46 In the context of a boom of initiatives aiming at boosting a circular economy within the European
47 Union,¹⁻³ it is the responsibility of researchers to provide policy-makers with the data and tools
48 needed to make informed decisions. How to measure the circularity of resources is one of the
49 key questions that must be addressed in order to assess the performance of a circular economy.

50

51 A number of approaches have been recently presented to tackle this issue. One study defined a
52 global circularity metrics as the share of material inputs into the global economy that are cycled.⁴
53 It estimated that the global economy was 9.1% circular in 2015. Although this indicator provides
54 insight into the global materials metabolism, policy implications cannot be directly derived from
55 it. Instead, a metrics that can be applied to systems design and operation is of more interest to
56 the decision-making processes, which usually take place at regional or local scale.

57

58 The consensus in the literature on circularity indicators is that they need to capture how the
59 quality of the recovered waste components affects the amount of primary resources they
60 displace. Accordingly, Moriguchi⁵ pointed out that the reduction in the requirement for primary
61 resources could be a good indicator of circularity. The disadvantage of this approach is that a
62 base scenario must be defined to calculate the indicator. Haupt et al.⁶ suggested that open-loop
63 and closed-loop recycling rates that reflect the efficiency of the recycling processes and the type
64 of application of the recycled components in their next life cycle stage should be used as
65 performance indicators for a circular economy. The duration of material retention within a
66 system has also been recommended as an indicator of circularity.⁷ These indicators do not
67 necessarily correlate with the quality of the recovered components and they do not reveal how
68 much of the recycled components are consumed again; i.e., to what extent the loop is closed.

69

70 The methodology proposed by Cobo et al.,⁸ which enables to track waste components within a
71 Circular Integrated Waste Management System (CIWMS), might help overcome these
72 limitations, since CIWMSs encompass not only waste management, but also the processing and
73 consumption of the components recovered from waste and the external raw materials that
74 eventually become waste.

75

76 This framework is applied to the study of the management of organic waste (OW) in the region
77 of Cantabria, in the north of Spain. The OW generated in Cantabria (83.5 kton in 2014) is
78 currently collected with other discarded household inorganic materials. The OW that is sorted
79 out at the regional mechanical-biological treatment facility is subjected to a windrow
80 composting process. Nonetheless, Directive 2008/98/EC⁹ does not allow the land application of
81 the bio-stabilized material derived from composting the OW separated from the mixed waste
82 stream; only the OW that has been source separated can be recycled. The expiration of the
83 regional authorization that permitted the sale of the bio-stabilized material as compost until
84 2018¹⁰ poses the pressing challenge of simultaneously managing OW and complying with the
85 legal restraints. However, the need to retrofit the regional OW management system also
86 represents an opportunity to implement new circularity practices.

87

88 The interest of recycling OW lies in the nutrients that the products that can potentially be
89 recovered contain. This study focuses on three essential nutrients to soil amendment: carbon
90 (C), nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P).

91

92 Enhancing the circularity of these nutrients within a CIWMS *a priori* seems to be a strategy that
93 will contribute to closing their natural biogeochemical cycles by avoiding the accumulation of
94 nutrients in one of the Earth's subsystems (atmosphere, hydrosphere, biosphere or lithosphere)
95 at a rate faster than the ecosystems can sustain. Thus, the relevance that a circular economy of

96 nutrients might have to global sustainability challenges should not be underestimated. On the
97 one hand, the forthcoming peak P production threatens future food security;¹¹ on the other, the
98 anthropogenic interference with the C and N biogeochemical cycles to meet the energy and food
99 demands has already caused the transgression of the estimated climate change and N cycle
100 planetary boundaries within which humanity is expected to operate safely.¹²

101

102 Since the nutrient cycles interact with each other,¹³ promoting the circularity of one nutrient
103 might have consequences on the biogeochemical cycles of the others. For instance, increasing
104 Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) stocks may exacerbate N₂O emissions,¹⁴ and an increased availability
105 of reactive N may lead to C sequestration as a result of biomass growth.¹⁵ Another counter-
106 effect related to the land application of the products recovered from OW is the accumulation of
107 surplus P in agricultural soils, because the N:P ratio in organic fertilizers is lower than the N:P
108 ratio required by crops.¹⁶⁻¹⁸

109

110 Therefore, it is clear that the circularity of C, N and P within a CIWMS and the main impacts
111 associated with the emissions of these elements to the environment (global warming, marine
112 eutrophication and freshwater eutrophication) must be analyzed jointly. Although the recovery
113 of nutrients is a subject that is drawing the attention of the scientific community,¹⁹⁻²³ the trade-
114 offs between these indicators have not been systematically explored in the literature yet.

115 Therefore, the objectives of this paper are the following:

- 116 - To propose a circularity indicator that can be applied to any non-renewable resource and
117 accounts for the extended service of the components recovered from waste.
- 118 - To optimize the OW management system in the region of Cantabria, setting as objective
119 functions the maximization of the circularity indicators of C, N and P, and the minimization
120 of the global warming, marine eutrophication and freshwater eutrophication impacts.

121

122

123 **METHODOLOGY**

124

125 The unit processes that can potentially be part of a CIWMS aiming at nutrient recovery from OW
126 were identified and a superstructure that comprises all the combinations of unit processes was
127 proposed (Figure 1). Material Flow Analysis (MFA), modular Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)²⁴ and
128 optimization tools were applied to determine the optimal configuration of the system.

129

130 The unit processes concerning the management of solid OW were modeled with EASETECH
131 2.3.6,²⁵ which provided their environmental impacts. The products recovered from OW were
132 assumed to be applied to land to grow corn, the main fodder crop grown in Cantabria.²⁶ The
133 nitrate and phosphate leaching losses, the emissions of CO₂, N₂O and NO, the amount of
134 Dissolved Organic Carbon (DOC) consumed by soil microorganisms, the flows of N and P uptaken
135 by corn and the amount of nutrients stored in soil per hectare of cultivated corn were calculated
136 with DNDC 9.5.²⁷ These results were transferred to EASETECH 2.3.6, where the

140 environmental impacts associated with the land application of the recovered products and corn
141 production were calculated.

142

143 The results obtained with DNDC and EASETECH were exported as parameters to GAMS 24.8.1,
144 where the problem was formulated. Figure 2 clarifies the data flows derived from the application
145 of this methodology.

Figure 2. Data flow diagram

150 The data required to characterize the unit processes that integrate the system are compiled in
151 the Supporting Information: waste composition (Appendix A), waste management unit
152 processes (Appendix B) and corn production subsystem (Appendix C).

153

154

155

156 **DEFINITION OF THE CIRCULARITY INDICATOR**

157

158 Figure 3 illustrates the flows of the component i of a given waste stream within a CIWMS. The
159 circularity indicator of component i (CI_i) is defined as the amount of component i that extends
160 its lifetime by providing a service in the upstream processes with respect to the amount of that
161 component present in the collected waste. Equation 1 shows how the CI_i is calculated for a set
162 of n recycling processes that enhance the properties of the waste component and m production
163 processes that valorize this component into products capable of providing a service.

$$CI_i = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n R_{ijk} \cdot \eta_{r_{ij}} \cdot \eta_{p_{ik}}}{W_i} \quad (1)$$

164 The variables needed for the calculation of CI_i are these:

- 165 - W_i . Amount of component i present in the waste stream (kg).
- 166 - R_{ijk} . Amount of component i that enters the recycling process j . The subsequently
167 recycled component i enters the production process k (kg).
- 168 - $\eta_{r_{ij}}$. Efficiency of the recycling process j for component i (kg of component i recovered
169 per kg of component i that enters the recycling process j).
- 170 - $\eta_{p_{ik}}$. Efficiency of the production process k for component i (kg of component i
171 processed per kg of component i that enters process k).

172

173

174

Figure 3. Simplified CIWMS

175

176 The proposed indicator indirectly accounts for the quality of the recovered components by
 177 quantifying how much of the recycled component can actually be consumed. This indicator does
 178 not account *per se* for the degradation of the waste components after successive cycles, but if
 179 the selected time horizon of the study is wide enough, a dynamic analysis should show how for
 180 a sustained service demand, the external supply of component i ($\sum_{k=1}^m E_{ik}$) must increase due
 181 to the degradation of the recovered component.

182

183

184 **Nutrient circularity indicators**

185

186 The circularity indicators of N and P (CI_N and CI_P) were defined as the amount of nutrient i that
 187 is recycled, applied to land and uptaken by corn with respect to the amount of nutrient i present
 188 in the collected OW.

189

190 The same definition cannot be applied to the C circularity indicator (CI_C), since the C captured
191 by vegetation in the photosynthesis process does not come from the soil but from the
192 atmosphere, a global C sink.

193

194 Besides improving the water-holding capacity of soil and the ability of soil to retain cations in a
195 plant available form, contributing to C sequestration and promoting the formation of soil
196 structure,^{28,29} the purpose of applying a source of C to land is to feed the soil microorganisms.
197 When these microorganisms decompose the SOC, the decomposed C is partially lost as CO₂, and
198 DOC is produced as an intermediate that can be consumed by the soil microorganisms.³⁰ These
199 microbes are also responsible for the N fixation, ammonification and nitrification processes that
200 release N compounds that plants can assimilate. Thus, these microbes are essential for crop
201 production.

202

203 Consequently, CI_C was defined as the ratio between the kg of DOC that is recycled, applied to
204 land and consumed by microbes with respect to the amount of C present in the collected waste.

205

206 The values of $\eta_{r_{ij}}$ and $\eta_{p_{ik}}$ required for the calculation of the circularity indicators are compiled
207 in Appendix D of the Supporting Information.

208

209

210 **PROBLEM FORMULATION**

211

212 A single-period Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) problem was formulated for the
213 optimization of the incoming material flows (waste and recovered products) to the green shaded
214 unit processes in Figure 1. The problem was optimized according to these objective functions:
215 the circularity indicators of the studied nutrients, which must be maximized ($CI_C(x, y)$,

216 $CI_N(x, y)$, and $CI_P(x, y)$), and the environmental impacts of the system to be minimized (global
 217 warming $GW(x, y)$, marine eutrophication $MEU(x, y)$ and freshwater eutrophication
 218 $FWE(x, y)$).

219

220 After verifying the trade-offs between the objective functions, a multi-objective MILP problem

221 was formulated as follows:

$$222 \min U(x, y) = \{GW(x, y), MEU(x, y), -CI_N(x, y), -CI_P(x, y)\} \text{ s. t. } \begin{cases} h(x, y) = 0 \\ g(x, y) \leq 0 \\ x \in \mathfrak{R}^n \\ y \in \{0, 1\}^m \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

223

224

225 The equations that describe the behavior of the system ($h(x, y) = 0$) are based on the mass
 226 balances of the unit processes. The problem is subjected to these restrictions ($g(x, y) \leq 0$):

- 227 - The area fertilized with the recovered products cannot exceed the available area to grow
 228 corn in Cantabria.
- 229 - The amount of biodegradable waste sent to landfill must be lower than 35% of the domestic
 230 waste generated in 1995, as established by Directive 1999/31/EC.³¹
- 231 - A waste stream of a given composition cannot be split between tunnel and windrows
 232 composting.
- 233 - Source separated organic waste (SS-OW) and the OW that is sorted out from the
 234 commingled waste stream (mix-OW) cannot be mixed in any composting processes.

235

236 The GAMS model comprises a total of 844 equations, 19 inequations, 817 continuous variables
 237 and 28 discrete variables. The main input parameters to the models are the source separation
 238 rate, the total area available for corn production and the amount of OW generated yearly in
 239 Cantabria.

240

241 Different waste collection systems for SS-OW and commingled waste were modeled. It was
242 considered that the composition of SS-OW is 98% OW and 2% impurities, which is consistent
243 with documented source separation experiences.³² Two scenarios (neglecting and considering
244 the current legislative framework) were analyzed:

245 - **Pre-Directive scenario.** Mix-OW can be recycled. The source separation rate is 0% and no
246 recycling target is set. The blue arrows in Figure 1 represent the flows of OW that can only
247 be composted in this scenario.

248 - **Post-Directive scenario.** Mix-OW cannot be recycled. In order to comply with the 50% OW
249 recycling target established by the Cantabrian waste management plan¹⁰ for 2020, a 50%
250 source separation rate is set and an additional restriction is added to the model to ensure
251 that 50% of the collected OW is composted or anaerobically digested.

252

253 The multi-objective optimization problem was solved with the CPLEX solver and the ϵ -constraint
254 method.³³

255

256

257 **MODEL DESCRIPTION**

258

259 The dotted line in Figure 1 represents the boundary that separates the studied CIWMS from the
260 ecosphere (which provides the natural resources consumed by the system and a sink for the
261 generated environmental burdens) and the rest of the technosphere.

262

263 The developed model describes the behavior of the unit processes shown in Figure 1 (those that
264 already belong to Cantabria's waste management system are represented with a discontinuous
265 line). Anaerobic digestion, tunnel composting, windrow composting, incineration and landfill
266 handle the solid OW, whereas the ammonia stripping and absorption and the struvite

267 precipitation unit processes recover nutrients from the liquid digestate (LD) produced in the
268 anaerobic digestion (which can only process SS-OW). The remaining liquor is sent to a
269 wastewater treatment plant. Incineration and landfill can also handle the rejects generated by
270 the other unit processes. A detailed description of the unit processes can be found in Cobo et
271 al.³⁴

272

273 Although crops are the result of human interventions in the technosphere, they produce natural
274 biotic resources. Hence, the boundary between technosphere and ecosphere is difficult to
275 identify for agricultural soils.³⁵ One of the strategies recommended by Notarnicola et al.³⁶ to
276 overcome the duality of agricultural soils is to consider the impacts of crop production on soil.
277 In this study the land application of the recovered products and the production of corn were
278 modeled as a unit process. Although the system was optimized for only 1 year of operation, the
279 selected 100-year time horizon enabled to account for the loss of soil quality due to soil nutrient
280 depletion caused by the production of consecutive crops, which affected the annual corn
281 production.

282

283 The nutrient uptake efficiencies of corn (shown in Appendix D) differ for each type of applied
284 product (bio-stabilized material, compost, digestate, struvite and ammonium sulphate), mostly
285 because they are highly dependent on the presence of C in soil.

286

287 As shown in Appendix C, P is in excess with respect to the amount of N required by corn in all
288 the recovered products except for ammonium sulphate. Consequently, the nutrient flows were
289 modeled so that the optimal approach to corn production can be either based on one of these
290 strategies or on a combination of them:

291 - Application of the amount of recovered product needed to cover the corn N requirements.
292 Unless ammonium sulphate is recovered, excess P is applied to soil, leading to freshwater
293 eutrophication.

294 - Application of the amount of recovered product needed to cover the corn P requirements.
295 The N requirements are fulfilled with an industrial fertilizer (NH_4NO_3).

296 - Application of industrial N and P fertilizers (NH_4NO_3 and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$).

297

298 The alternative combinations of *k* corn production processes that can emerge from the
299 application of these strategies are shown in Figure 4. The N and P requirements of corn are
300 defined as the amounts of these nutrients that yield the maximum average annual crop
301 production that can be achieved in a 100-year timeframe with industrial N and P fertilizers.
302 Assuming an 80% collection rate of the produced corn grain, it corresponds to a net production
303 of 7.11 tons of corn grain per ha per year.

304

305 Corn enters the food production and consumption subsystem, which comprises the upstream
306 processes that transform corn and the other food commodities consumed in Cantabria into OW.
307 It composes the background subsystem of the CIWMS because its configuration does not affect
308 the results of the study;³⁷ only the flows and the composition of its inputs and outputs (corn and
309 waste) that connect it to other unit processes are calculated.

310

311 According to Cobo et al.,⁸ the primary function of CIWMSs is to recover waste components so
312 that their service life in the upstream processes can be extended. In this case study the elements
313 recovered from OW are subsequently used for land fertilization and soil conditioning. Since the
314 studied CIWMS encompasses the entire corn production of the region, the functional unit
315 selected to perform the LCA of the system is defined as the area available to grow corn in
316 Cantabria (4810 ha).³⁸

317

318 An attributional LCA approach was applied. Energy generation (from the incineration of OW and
319 the combustion of the biogas generated in the anaerobic digestion and landfill unit processes)
320 is considered the secondary system function. The direct substitution method was applied by
321 expanding the system boundaries to include the generation of electricity from the Spanish grid
322 mix. A 100% substitution ratio was assumed.

323

324 **Figure 4.** Possible combinations of inputs to the corn production subsystem

325

326 The characterization factors of each emission were calculated with the hierarchical 100-year
327 perspective of ReCiPe 1.11. Following the rationale explained by Cobo et al.,^{8,34} only the biogenic
328 C present in animal and vegetable food waste was considered neutral; the CO₂ derived from the
329 decomposition of SOC was also quantified as fossil C.

330 Regarding the limitations of the model, the environmental impacts related to capital goods and
331 the implementation of a source separation system for OW were excluded from the analysis. On
332 the other hand, this work assumes that all the P is in mineral form and therefore accessible for
333 plants, although studies have shown that most of the P in the products recovered from OW is in
334 mineral form, but not all of it.³⁹⁻⁴²

335

336

337 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

338

339 The results of the problem optimization determine the system configuration; i.e., the unit
340 processes that the system comprises and their incoming flows of waste and recovered products.

341 The values of the objective functions and the decision variables that optimize each objective
342 function for the two studied scenarios are compiled in Figures 5 and 6. Figure 5 shows the flows
343 of OW and LD handled by each unit process for the maximization of the circularity indicators

344 (Figure 5a) and the minimization of the environmental impacts (Figure 5b). The flows of the
345 recovered products into the corn production unit processes and the area fertilized with the
346 recovered products can be seen in Figure 6. The contribution of the unit processes to the

347 environmental impacts of the optimal configurations of the system in each scenario are shown
348 in Appendix E of the Supporting Information.

Figure 5. Incoming waste flows to the selected unit processes

349

350

351

352 The flows of OW shown in Figure 5 are lower in the Pre-Directive scenario because part of the
 353 OW present in the mixed waste ends up in the inorganic waste stream after the trommel
 354 separation required for the pretreatment of mixed waste.

355

356 There are multiple optimal solutions to the maximization of a given circularity indicator, because

357 the unit processes that manage the rejects do not contribute to closing the nutrient loops within

358 the system. By analogy, in the Post-Directive scenario where mix-OW cannot be recycled, the
 359 selection of any unit process for its management will result in the same circularity indicators.
 360 This is the reason Figure 5a only shows the unit processes that contribute to recirculate nutrients
 361 within the system.
 362
 363 The amount of P present in the mix-OW collected in the Pre-Directive scenario is more than
 364 enough to cover the P requirements of the corn produced in Cantabria under the hypothesis of
 365 this work. However, the N present in OW cannot fertilize all the land available for corn
 366 production in any of the studied scenarios. As Figure 6 shows, more area is fertilized with the
 367 recovered products in the Pre-Directive scenario because of the higher amount of OW that can
 368 be recycled.

369
 370 **Figure 6.** Incoming flows of recovered products to the corn production unit processes
 371

372 The optimization of some objective functions provides duplicate or very similar results
373 (freshwater eutrophication and CI_P on the one hand, CI_C and different circularity indicators in
374 each scenario on the other). Thus, freshwater eutrophication and CI_C were excluded from the
375 next part of the study, focused on a multi-objective optimization of the other four objective
376 functions.

377

378 Figure 7 shows the Pareto fronts of the two scenarios, in which each point is better than the
379 others in at least one of the values of the objective functions. The global warming and marine
380 eutrophication in Figure 7 are normalized with respect to the maximum value of the two
381 scenarios.

382

383 If industrial fertilizers, ammonium sulphate or struvite are exclusively applied to soil, the corn
384 Nitrogen Use Efficiency (NUE, defined as the fraction of N input harvested as product)⁴³ decays
385 over time because of the depletion of SOC. The opposite occurs when bio-stabilized material,
386 compost and digestate are applied, due to their C rich composition. However, the mean NUE
387 obtained for the 100-year time horizon if products that only contain inorganic N are applied to
388 land is higher than the NUE achieved after the soil application of the C containing recovered
389 products, because the share of plant available inorganic N in the latter is low. This implies that
390 more N leaches when the recovered products with a high organic N content are applied to land.
391 Consequently, in both scenarios the marine eutrophication impacts increase with the CI_N , being
392 the values of these two objective functions higher in the Post-Directive scenario. A similar
393 correlation cannot be established between CI_P and freshwater eutrophication because, unlike
394 N, which tends to leach as nitrate when it is applied to soil, P is strongly sorbed onto soil particles;
395 in fact its major environmental losses can be attributed to erosion.⁴⁴

396

397 The Pre-Directive scenarios, where the minimum amount of OW that must be recycled is not
398 restricted, rely strongly on incineration and the application of industrial fertilizers. Although the
399 production of fertilizers is very energy intensive,⁴⁵ the carbon footprint associated with the land
400 application of these products is lower than that of the C containing recovered products, a
401 fraction of which degrades to CO₂ after their land application. Thus, as Figure 7a shows, in the
402 Pre-Directive scenario as CI_N increases, the CO₂-eq emissions increase too.

403

404 Anaerobic digestion is the unit process that handles OW with the lowest carbon footprint.
405 Hence, the minimum carbon footprint achieved at the Post-Directive scenario, the only one
406 where SS-OW can be subjected to anaerobic digestion, is lower than in the Pre-Directive
407 scenario. Moreover, since the N recycling efficiency of anaerobic digestion and the LD unit
408 processes is higher than that of the other unit processes, the land application of the products
409 derived from anaerobic digestion also maximizes CI_N . Therefore, as shown in Figure 7b, in the
410 Post-Directive scenario as the CI_N increases, the carbon footprint of the system decreases.

411

412 Regarding CI_P , it shows a similar trend to the CI_N in the Pre-Directive scenario, whereas no clear
413 trend can be appreciated in the Post-Directive scenario, where the maximization of CI_P is
414 based on the application of compost to cover the soil P requirements, and the maximization of
415 CI_N on the application of ammonium sulphate and solid digestate to fulfill the soil N needs,
416 which leads to the accumulation of P in soil. The values of CI_P are lower in the Post-Directive
417 scenario.

418

419 Figure 7 proves that the environmental impacts associated with increasing the circularity of
420 nutrients cannot be overlooked. Whereas in the pre-Directive scenario there is a clear opposite
421 trend between the environmental impacts and the circularity of nutrients, the behavior of the

422 system in the Post-Directive scenario, subject to more restrictions and with more unit processes
423 available, is more complex.

424

425 The findings of this study suggest that increasing the source separation rate of OW leads to a
426 reduction in the carbon footprint of the system. Although the results clearly indicate that
427 increasing the circularity of N has detrimental eutrophication impacts, these are highly
428 dependent on the sensitivity of the receiving environment,⁴⁶ and thus general conclusions
429 cannot be drawn.

430

431 Before selecting a system configuration that meets the sustainability concerns and satisfies the
432 interests of all the stakeholders involved in waste management and the purchase of the
433 recovered products, a trade-off between the studied indicators must be identified. However,
434 the feasibility of any system configuration cannot be demonstrated until an economic analysis
435 is carried out. Hence, future research should look into the economic evaluation of the system.

436

437

Figure 7. Pareto points

453 **NOMENCLATURE**

454

455 C – Carbon

456 CI_C – Carbon circularity indicator

457 CI_N – Nitrogen circularity indicator

458 CI_P – Phosphorus circularity indicator

459 CIWMS – Circular Integrated Waste Management System

460 DOC – Dissolved Organic Carbon

461 LCA – Life Cycle Assessment

462 LD – Liquid digestate

463 MFA – Material Flow Analysis

464 MILP – Mixed Integer Linear Programming

465 mix-OW – Organic waste separated from the mixed waste stream

466 N – Nitrogen

467 NUE – Nitrogen Use Efficiency

468 OW – Organic waste

469 P – Phosphorus

470 SOC – Soil Organic Carbon

471 SS-OW – Source separated organic waste

472

473

474 **SUPPORTING INFORMATION**

475

476 Waste composition, model data, LCA results.

477

478

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480

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485 **REFERENCES**

486

- 487 1. *Closing the loop - An EU action plan for the Circular Economy*. European Commission:
488 Brussels, 2015; [http://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:8a8ef5e8-99a0-](http://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:8a8ef5e8-99a0-11e5-b3b7-01aa75ed71a1.0012.02/DOC_1&format=PDF)
489 [11e5-b3b7-01aa75ed71a1.0012.02/DOC_1&format=PDF](http://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:8a8ef5e8-99a0-11e5-b3b7-01aa75ed71a1.0012.02/DOC_1&format=PDF).
- 490 2. Domenech, T.; Bahn-Walkowiak, B. Transition Towards a Resource Efficient Circular
491 Economy in Europe: Policy Lessons From the EU and the Member States. *Ecol.*
492 *Econ.* **2017**; DOI 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.11.001.
- 493 3. Delgado-Aguilar, M.; Tarrés, Q.; Pèlach, M. À.; Mutjé, P.; Fullana-I-Palmer, P. Are
494 Cellulose Nanofibers a Solution for a More Circular Economy of Paper Products? *Environ.*
495 *Sci. Technol.* **2015**, *49*, 12206-12213.
- 496 4. *The circularity gap report. An analysis of the circular state of the global economy*. Circle
497 economy: Amsterdam, 2018; <https://www.circularity-gap.world/report>.
- 498 5. Moriguchi, Y. Material flow indicators to measure progress toward a sound material-
499 cycle society. *J. Mater. Cycles Waste Manage.* **2007**, *9*, 112-120.
- 500 6. Haupt, M.; Vadenbo, C.; Hellweg, S. Do We Have the Right Performance Indicators for
501 the Circular Economy?: Insight into the Swiss Waste Management System. *J. Ind.*
502 *Ecol.* **2017**, *21*, 615-627.
- 503 7. Franklin-Johnson, E.; Figge, F.; Canning, L. Resource duration as a managerial indicator
504 for Circular Economy performance. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2016**, *133*, 589-598.

- 505 8. Cobo, S.; Dominguez-Ramos, A.; Irabien, A. From linear to circular integrated waste
506 management systems: A review of methodological approaches. *Resour. Conserv.*
507 *Recycl.* **2017**. DOI 10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.08.003.
- 508 9. Directive on waste and repealing certain Directives. Directive 2008/98/EC, 2008;
509 <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/En/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32008L0098>.
- 510 10. *Plan de residuos de la Comunidad Autónoma de Cantabria 2016 – 2022*; Gobierno de
511 Cantabria, Consejería de Universidades e Investigación, Medio Ambiente y Política
512 Social: Santander, 2016;
513 http://www.medioambientecantabria.es/documentos_contenidos/64293_2.versioninicialPR.pdf.
514
- 515 11. Cordell, D.; Drangert, J.-L.; White, S. The story of phosphorus: Global food security and
516 food for thought. *Global Environ. Change* **2009**, *19*, 292-305.
- 517 12. Rockström, J.; Steffen, W.; Noone, K.; Persson, A.; Chapin III, F. S.; Lambin, E.; Lenton, T.
518 M.; Scheffer, M.; Folke, C.; Schellnhuber, H. J.; Nykvist, B.; de Wit, C. A.; Hughes, T.; van
519 der Leeuw, S.; Rodhe, H.; Sörlin, S.; Snyder, P. K.; Costanza, R.; Svedin, U.; Falkenmark,
520 M.; Karlberg, L.; Corell, R. W.; Fabry, V. J.; Hansen, J.; Walker, B.; Liverman, D.;
521 Richardson, K.; Crutzen, P.; Foley, J. Planetary boundaries: Exploring the safe operating
522 space for humanity. *Ecol. Soc.* **2009**, *14*(2):32.
- 523 13. Likens, G.E.; Bormann, F.H.; Johnson, N.M. Interactions between major biogeochemical
524 cycles in terrestrial ecosystems. In *Some perspectives of the major biogeochemical*
525 *cycles*; Likens, G.E., Ed.; John Wiley & Sons: Chichester, 1981; pp 93-109.
- 526 14. Lal, R. Soil carbon sequestration impacts on global climate change and food
527 security. *Science* **2004**, *304*, 1623-1627.
- 528 15. Kroeze, C.; Hofstra, N.; Ivens, W.; Löhr, A.; Stokal, M.; van Wijnen, J. The links between
529 global carbon, water and nutrient cycles in an urbanizing world - the case of coastal
530 eutrophication. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustainability* **2013**, *5*, 566-572.

- 531 16. Hanserud, O. S.; Cherubini, F.; Øgaard, A. F.; Müller, D. B.; Brattebø, H. Choice of mineral
532 fertilizer substitution principle strongly influences LCA environmental benefits of
533 nutrient cycling in the agri-food system. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2018**, *615*, 219-227.
- 534 17. Schoumans, O.F. Phosphorus leaching from soils: process description, risk assessment
535 and mitigation. Ph.D. Dissertation, Wageningen University, Wageningen, The
536 Netherlands, 2015.
- 537 18. Rowe, H.; Withers, P. J. A.; Baas, P.; Chan, N. I.; Doody, D.; Holiman, J.; Jacobs, B.; Li, H.;
538 MacDonald, G. K.; McDowell, R.; Sharpley, A. N.; Shen, J.; Taheri, W.; Wallenstein, M.;
539 Weintraub, M. N. Integrating legacy soil phosphorus into sustainable nutrient
540 management strategies for future food, bioenergy and water security. *Nutr. Cycl.*
541 *Agroecosyst.* **2016**, *104*, 393-412.
- 542 19. Yao, Y.; Martinez-Hernandez, E.; Yang, A. Modelling nutrient flows in a simplified local
543 food-energy-water system. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* **2018**. DOI
544 10.1016/j.resconrec.2018.02.022.
- 545 20. Tonini, D.; Martinez-Sanchez, V.; Astrup, T. F. Material resources, energy, and nutrient
546 recovery from waste: Are waste refineries the solution for the future? *Environ. Sci.*
547 *Technol.* **2013**, *47*, 8962-8969.
- 548 21. Wang, X.; Guo, M.; Koppelaar, R. H. E. M.; Van Dam, K. H.; Triantafyllidis, C. P.; Shah, N.
549 A Nexus Approach for Sustainable Urban Energy-Water-Waste Systems Planning and
550 Operation. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2018**, *52*, 3257-3266.
- 551 22. Knoop, C.; Tietze, M.; Dornack, C.; Raab, T. Fate of nutrients and heavy metals during
552 two-stage digestion and aerobic post-treatment of municipal organic waste. *Bioresour.*
553 *Technol.* **2018**, *251*, 238-248.
- 554 23. Yoshida, H.; ten Hoeve, M.; Christensen, T. H.; Bruun, S.; Jensen, L. S.; Scheutz, C. Life
555 cycle assessment of sewage sludge management options including long-term impacts
556 after land application. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2018**, *174*, 538-547.

- 557 24. Steubing, B.; Mutel, C.; Suter, F.; Hellweg, S. Streamlining scenario analysis and
558 optimization of key choices in value chains using a modular LCA approach. *Int. J. Life*
559 *Cycle Assess.* **2016**, *21*, 510-522.
- 560 25. Clavreul, J.; Baumeister, H.; Christensen, T. H.; Damgaard, A. An environmental
561 assessment system for environmental technologies. *Environ. Model. Softw.* **2014**, *60*,
562 18-30.
- 563 26. *Los pastos en Cantabria y su aprovechamiento. Memoria*; Centro de Investigación y
564 Formación Agrarias: Santander, 2006;
565 <http://cifacantabria.org/Documentos/memoria.pdf>.
- 566 27. Gilhespy, S. L.; Anthony, S.; Cardenas, L.; Chadwick, D.; del Prado, A.; Li, C.; Misselbrook,
567 T.; Rees, R. M.; Salas, W.; Sanz-Cobena, A.; Smith, P.; Tilston, E. L.; Topp, C. F. E.; Vetter,
568 S.; Yeluripati, J. B. First 20 years of DNDC (DeNitrification DeComposition): Model
569 evolution. *Ecol. Model.* **2014**, *292*, 51-62.
- 570 28. Lehmann, J.; Kleber, M. The contentious nature of soil organic matter. *Nature* **2015**, *528*,
571 60-68.
- 572 29. Foley, J. A.; DeFries, R.; Asner, G. P.; Barford, C.; Bonan, G.; Carpenter, S. R.; Chapin, F.
573 S.; Coe, M. T.; Daily, G. C.; Gibbs, H. K.; Helkowski, J. H.; Holloway, T.; Howard, E. A.;
574 Kucharik, C. J.; Monfreda, C.; Patz, J. A.; Prentice, I. C.; Ramankutty, N.; Snyder, P. K.
575 Global consequences of land use. *Science* **2005**, *309*, 570-574.
- 576 30. Gougoulias, C.; Clark, J. M.; Shaw, L. J. The role of soil microbes in the global carbon
577 cycle: Tracking the below-ground microbial processing of plant-derived carbon for
578 manipulating carbon dynamics in agricultural systems. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* **2014**, *94*, 2362-
579 2371.
- 580 31. Council Directive on the landfill of waste. Council Directive 1999/31/EC,
581 1999;[http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-](http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31999L0031&from=EN)
582 [content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31999L0031&from=EN](http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31999L0031&from=EN).

- 583 32. *Source separation of MSW. An overview of the source separation and separate collection*
584 *of the digestible fraction of household waste, and of other similar wastes from*
585 *municipalities, aimed to be used as feedstock for anaerobic digestion in biogas plants;*
586 IEA bioenergy: 2013; [http://task37.ieabioenergy.com/files/daten-](http://task37.ieabioenergy.com/files/daten-redaktion/download/Technical%20Brochures/source_separation_web.pdf)
587 [redaktion/download/Technical%20Brochures/source_separation_web.pdf](http://task37.ieabioenergy.com/files/daten-redaktion/download/Technical%20Brochures/source_separation_web.pdf).
- 588 33. Copado-Méndez, P. J.; Pozo, C.; Guillén-Gosálbez, G.; Jiménez, L. Enhancing the ϵ -
589 constraint method through the use of objective reduction and random sequences:
590 Application to environmental problems. *Comput. Chem. Eng.* **2016**, *87*, 36-48.
- 591 34. Cobo, S.; Dominguez-Ramos, A.; Irabien, A. Minimization of Resource Consumption and
592 Carbon Footprint of a Circular Organic Waste Valorization System. *ACS Sustainable*
593 *Chem. Eng.* **2018**, *6*, 3493-3501.
- 594 35. Crenna, E.; Sozzo, S.; Sala, S. Natural biotic resources in LCA: Towards an impact
595 assessment model for sustainable supply chain management. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2018**, *172*,
596 3669-3684.
- 597 36. Notarnicola, B.; Sala, S.; Anton, A.; McLaren, S. J.; Saouter, E.; Sonesson, U. The role of
598 life cycle assessment in supporting sustainable agri-food systems: A review of the
599 challenges. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2017**, *140*, 399-409.
- 600 37. Frischknecht, R. Life cycle inventory analysis for decision-making. Scope-dependent
601 inventory system models and context-specific joint product allocation. Ph.D.
602 dissertation, Swiss Federal Institute of Technology, Zurich, 1998.
- 603 38. *Encuesta sobre superficies y rendimientos cultivos*; Ministerio de Agricultura y Pesca,
604 Alimentación y Medio Ambiente: Madrid, 2017;
605 [http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-](http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/agricultura/esyrce/)
606 [agrarias/agricultura/esyrce/](http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/agricultura/esyrce/).

- 607 39. Frossard, E.; Skrabal, P.; Sinaj, S.; Bangerter, F.; Traore, O. Forms and exchangeability of
608 inorganic phosphate in composted solid organic wastes. *Nutr. Cycl. Agroecosyst.* **2002**,
609 *62*, 103-113.
- 610 40. Gagnon, B.; Demers, I.; Ziadi, N.; Chantigny, M. H.; Parent, L. -.; Forge, T. A.; Larney, F.
611 J.; Buckley, K. E. Forms of phosphorus in composts and in compostamended soils
612 following incubation. *Can. J. Soil Sci.* **2012**, *92*, 711-721.
- 613 41. García-Albacete, M.; Martín, A.; Cartagena, M. C. Fractionation of phosphorus
614 biowastes: Characterisation and environmental risk. *Waste Manage.* **2012**, *32*, 1061-
615 1068.
- 616 42. Hansen, T. L.; Bhandar, G. S.; Christensen, T. H.; Bruun, S.; Jensen, L. S. Life cycle
617 modelling of environmental impacts of application of processed organic municipal solid
618 waste on agricultural land (Easewaste). *Waste Manage. Res.* **2006**, *24*, 153-166.
- 619 43. Zhang, X.; Davidson, E. A.; Mauzerall, D. L.; Searchinger, T. D.; Dumas, P.; Shen, Y.
620 Managing nitrogen for sustainable development. *Nature* **2015**, *528*, 51-59.
- 621 44. Esculier, F.; Le Noë, J.; Barles, S.; Billen, G.; Créno, B.; Garnier, J.; Lesavre, J.; Petit, L.;
622 Tabuchi, J. P. (2018). The biogeochemical imprint of human metabolism in Paris
623 Megacity: A regionalized analysis of a water-agro-food system. *J. Hydrol.* **2018**,
624 doi:10.1016/j.jhydrol.2018.02.043.
- 625 45. Snyder, C. S.; Bruulsema, T. W.; Jensen, T. L.; Fixen, P. E. Review of greenhouse gas
626 emissions from crop production systems and fertilizer management effects. *Agric.*
627 *Ecosyst. Environ.* **2009**, *133*, 247-266.
- 628 46. De Jonge, V. N.; Elliott, M.; Orive, E. Causes, historical development, effects and future
629 challenges of a common environmental problem: Eutrophication. *Hydrobiologia* **2002**,
630 *475-476*, 1-19.